

Stochastic optimization framework for hybridization of existing offshore wind farms with wave energy and floating photovoltaic systems

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ABSTRACT

Due to the complementarity of renewable energy sources, there has been a focus on technology hybridization in recent years. In the area of hybrid offshore power plants, the current research projects mostly focus on the combinational implementation of wind, solar, and wave energy technologies. Accordingly, considering the already existing offshore wind farms, there is the potential for the implementation of hybrid power plants by adding wave energy converters and floating photovoltaics. In this work, a stochastic sizing model is developed for the hybridization of existing offshore wind farms using wave energy converters and floating photovoltaics considering the export cable capacity limitation. The problem is modeled from an investor perspective to maximize the economic profits of the hybridization, while the costs and revenues regarding the existing units and the export cable are excluded. Furthermore, to tackle the uncertainties of renewable energy generation, as well as the energy price, a scenario generation method based on copula theory is proposed to consider the dependency structure between the different random variables. Altogether, the hybridization study is modeled in a mixed integer linear programming optimization framework considering the net present value of the project as the objective function. The results showed that hybrid-sources-based energy generation provided the highest economic profit in the studied cases in the different geographical locations. Furthermore, the technical specifications of the farms have also been considerably improved providing more stable energy generation, guaranteeing a minimum level of power in a high share of the time, and with a better utilization of the capacity of the cable while the curtailment of energy is maintained within the acceptable range.

1. Introduction

Due to the current policies towards net-zero emissions, the share of renewable energy sources (RESs) in electrical systems is continuously increasing (Pata et al., 2023). Among them, wind energy has always been focused due to advancements in the technologies and all the benefits they provide in reliable and economic renewable energy generation (Vargas et al., 2019). Thanks to all the advantages of implementing wind power plants in the offshore sector, the installed capacity in the marine area has been considerably increased in recent years with an anticipation of continuing growth towards reaching the energy transition targets (Cheng and Hughes, 2023).

As another step towards decarbonization, in many recent projects, hybrid energy systems have been focused due to the complementarity of RESs and the synergies in the joint implementation of them whether in the small-scale cases or in the energy farms (Al-Rawashdeh et al., 2023).

In the context of the marine sector, wave (Pérez-Collazo et al., 2015) and solar (Ara et al., 2021) energy technologies have been considered as the main alternative sources besides wind energy to implement hybrid power plants.

Wave energy generally provides more consistent power generation capability with less fluctuations. According to the studies in the literature, the wave energy is more predictable (Astariz and Iglesias, 2016); it can also bring synergies while being implemented in hybrid farms besides wind turbines (Fusco et al., 2010). It should be emphasized that advancements are observed in decreasing the implementation cost of Wave Energy Converters (WECs) in recent years while further decrease is anticipated as the technology improves (Joensen and Bingham, 2024); furthermore, as they have demonstrated successful implementation for long periods of time including the harsh sea and ocean conditions, the path is paved towards the large-scale integration of recent technologies of WECs into the electrical energy systems.

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Table 1
Comparison of the study with the papers in the literature.

Reference	Existing park modeling		Candidate new RES units			Uncertainty		Optimization	
	WTs existing in the park	Offshore cable capacity limitation	WEC	FPV	WT	Scenario-based RES generation	Dependency of the random variables	RES Sizing	Framework/software for RES sizing
Vasileiou et al., 2017	×	×	✓	×	✓	×	×	×	×
Wen et al., 2022	×	×	✓	×	✓	×	×	×	×
Gao et al., 2022	✓	×	✓	×	×	×	×	×	×
Kluger et al., 2023	✓	✓	✓	×	×	×	×	×	×
Jahangir et al., 2020a	×	×	✓	✓	✓	×	×	✓	Homer
Jahangir et al., 2020b	×	×	✓	✓	✓	×	×	✓	Homer
Ramos et al., 2022	✓	×	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×
Golroodbari et al., 2021	✓	✓	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	Examination of a solution set
This work	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	MILP

As the other source of energy, there has been also a focus on the implementation of Floating PV (FPV) units in the marine environment in recent years (Gorjian et al., 2021). FPV can bring several benefits over land-based PVs; the exclusion of the need for land space and the increase of the energy generation capability due to the lower temperature are among the ones that can be stated for the marine sector. Furthermore, it should be emphasized that there are limitations in the spaces available for the implementation of FPV in inland areas; this is also another important motivation for the implementation of FPV in marine areas (Delacroix et al., 2023). With a focus on the challenges of such a new theory in energy generation, there have been important steps taken in the practical implementation of FPV systems in harsh sea conditions (Sall, 2023). Altogether, with the advancement of the involved technologies, the implementation of higher-capacity FPV farms can be anticipated in the upcoming year. This way, there will be also a strong potential for taking advantage of the joint implementation of solar energy in hybrid offshore farms.

In general, based on the stated alternative sources named for the hybridization, the hybrid farms can provide several benefits over the existing single source ones that are mainly the wind-turbine-based parks; less variability of power production (Rasool et al., 2022), better predictability (Saenz-Aguirre et al., 2022), lower implementation and maintenance costs due to shared facilities (López et al., 2020), less environmental impact (Loukogeorgaki et al., 2018), and shared marine area (Astariz et al., 2016) as well as sustainable use of the marine sources are some of the important benefits provided in hybrid farms.

There are also studies in the literature focusing on the challenges and opportunities of joint implementation of the energy sources where a variety of technical (Rasool et al., 2022) and economic (Golroodbari et al., 2021) assessments are applied regarding hybrid offshore power plants. Siting of the multi-source farms is studied in (Vasileiou et al., 2017) in which geographical analysis is done regarding the evaluation of the possibility of joint implementation of the different energy sources as well as the assessment of the benefits provided regarding the synergies. The effect of hybrid energy sources of offshore farms on the management and control of the storage systems is also investigated in (Kluger et al., 2023).

There are some studies on the determination of the optimal combination of different energy sources in a hybrid offshore farm. However, the literature on sizing the multi-source farms considering all wind, wave, and PV systems is limited. The main reference in this area is a sizing method for the off-grid/on-grid wind-solar-wave hybrid energy system with storage applied in (Jahangir et al., 2020a), which is implemented based on the use of HOMER software; such a study focusing on the Levelized Cost Of Energy (LCOE) is also implemented only on the stand-alone energy systems in (Jahangir et al., 2020b).

It should be noted that the reviewed studies focus on the formation of

new hybrid energy sources; in other words, they do not assess the implementation of hybrid energy sources in existing power plants. However, due to the presence of the considerable capacity of offshore wind power plants, there is the potential for the implementation of hybrid energy sources in the existing farms. Accordingly, an assessment of the benefits of implementing WECs besides the existing WTs is implemented in (Ramos et al., 2022); as clarified in the paper, the study is applied to a fixed size of each source while no optimization is carried out on the capacity and the share of WECs and WTs.

Furthermore, it is very important to consider the economic and environmental limitations in the expansion of the existing export cables of the offshore park while assuring effective utilization of the capacity of the connection with the onshore grid. Accordingly, in (Golroodbari et al., 2021) sizing study regarding the hybrid farm is implemented focusing on FPV capacity that can be added to a wind farm to improve the capacity factor of the cable. However, focusing only on FPV as the source of hybridization, the model of the study does not include the possibility of adding WECs to the farm. Furthermore, not including WTs as the alternative source for expansion of the farm, there cannot be a technical/economic comparison with a single-source park in the presence of extra turbines. Moreover, the uncertainties regarding energy generation and the wholesale market price are not modeled in the economic assessments of the study.

Altogether, regarding the studies available in the literature, there is a lack of a comprehensive optimization strategy for stochastic hybridization of existing offshore wind farms using wave and solar energies besides the possibility of adding more wind turbines considering the capacity limitation of the existing export electrical system as well as the uncertainties of the meteorological and energy price data. Such a study can be modeled as a capacity-optimization problem for the expansion of the farm aiming at the maximization of the benefits of the investor based on the available capacity of the already existing export cable of the park; hence, this study should only be focused on the economic assessments related the new units that will be added the farm.

According to the description, in this paper an optimization model has been developed for the hybridization of existing offshore wind farms using WECs and FPVs while having also WTs as the alternative for the expansion of farms; in order to tackle the uncertainties as well as the dependency of the random variables, the copula theory has been applied for scenario generation on wind speed, wave height, wave period, solar irradiance, temperature, and the wholesale market price of energy. The problem is developed in Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) formulation framework and the study is implemented in different locations to examine the effectiveness of the developed strategy for hybridization of existing farms. Sensitivity analysis has also been carried out regarding some of the economic parameters involved in the model and the results are discussed. Furthermore, technical assessments have

been carried out on the farm before and after the hybridization study to evaluate the effect of integrating the new sources on power variation, utilization of the capacity of the export cable of the farm, and guaranteeing a minimum level of power in a high share of the time during the year; such technical benefits can be also important for the TSOs and policymakers while assessing the possibility of incentivization of the hybridization projects.

A comparison of the current work with the studies in the literature is given in Table 1, and the contributions of the current study are summarized as follows.

- A MILP sizing model is proposed for hybridization/expansion of existing offshore power plants using wave, solar PV, and wind energy sources.
- The effects of the existing WTs and the cable capacity limitation are modeled in the NPV calculation for the hybridization project.
- Uncertainties are modeled in the optimization model regarding the energy generation by wind, wave, and solar sources as well as the wholesale market price.
- The copula theory is applied to model the dependency of random variables in the scenario generation process.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows; the mathematical model of the optimization problem as well as the implemented strategies for scenario generation and solving the problem are given in Section 2; the characterization of the studies and sensitivity analysis is provided in Section 3; the simulation results of implementing the hybridization studies in three different locations are given in Section 4; finally, the paper is concluded in Section 5.

2. Mathematical modeling and solution strategy

2.1. Mathematical modeling of the hybridization problem

As stated, the hybridization problem in this paper is studied from the investor perspective focusing on the Net Present Value (NPV) of the project as the Objective Function (OF) that is calculated in a stochastic framework to handle the uncertainties involved in the model; accordingly, the expected value of the OF in this study is represented as Equation (1) while further descriptions on the calculation of that is presented in Section 2.1.1.

$$OF : Max f = ENPV_{hybrid}. \quad (1)$$

in which $ENPV_{hybrid}$ is the expected NPV of the hybridization project excluding all the costs and revenues related to the existing WTs. It should be re-emphasized that besides the possibility of adding new sources of energy (WECs and FPVs), in this study, an alternative is also considered in the model for the expansion of the farm using extra WTs as a strategy to evaluate whether the hybrid sources bring more benefits to the project or increasing the capacity of the wind energy generation. Furthermore, supposing the capacity of the export system of the power plant to be equal to or more than the installed capacity of the existing units, the whole energy curtailments of the hybridization study are applied to the new units that will be added to the farm. Based on the descriptions and the other considerations for the implementation of the optimization in a stochastic framework, the overall constraints of the study are given in Equations (2)–(10).

$$n_{WT} \leq n_{WT}^{max} \quad (2)$$

$$n_{WEC} \leq n_{WEC}^{max} \quad (3)$$

$$n_{FPV} \leq n_{FPV}^{max} \quad (4)$$

$$n_{WT}, n_{WEC}, n_{FPV} \geq 0 \quad (5)$$

$$P_{WT}^s \leq n_{WT} \times P_{WT}^{s,max} \quad (6)$$

$$P_{WEC}^s \leq n_{WEC} \times P_{WEC}^{s,max} \quad (7)$$

$$P_{FPV}^s \leq n_{FPV} \times P_{FPV}^{s,max} \quad (8)$$

$$P_{WT}^s, P_{WEC}^s, P_{FPV}^s \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

$$P_{WT}^s + P_{WEC}^s + P_{FPV}^s \leq C_{EC} - P_e^s \quad (10)$$

in which n_{WT} , n_{WEC} , and n_{FPV} , are the integer variables of the problem indicating the number of WTs, WECs, and the FPVs; n_{WT}^{max} , n_{WEC}^{max} , and n_{FPV}^{max} are the maximum allowed number of each of them that can added to the farm; P_{WT}^s , P_{WEC}^s , and P_{FPV}^s are the variables presenting the power delivered by each source of energy through the cable in scenario s (MW) while $P_{WT}^{s,max}$, $P_{WEC}^{s,max}$, and $P_{FPV}^{s,max}$ are the power that can be generated by a single unit of WT, WEC, or FPV in the same scenario regarding the meteorological data (MW) calculated prior to optimization based on the descriptions provided in Section 2.1.2.; C_{EC} is the capacity of the export cable of the farm (MW), and P_e^s is the power generated by the WTs that are already existing in the farm before hybridization (MW); considering the same technology for both the existing WTs and the alternative ones that can be added to the farm, P_e^s is calculated using Equation (11).

$$P_e^s = n_{WT,e} \times P_{WT}^{s,max} \quad (11)$$

in which $n_{WT,e}$ is the number of existing WTs. Regarding the scenarios, it should be noted that in this study, they are formed regarding the wind speed, wave height, wave period, solar irradiance, temperature, and wholesale market price; further description of the scenario generation process is given in Section 2.2.

2.1.1. Expected net present value (ENPV) of the hybridization project

As clarified, in this paper, both costs and revenues of the existing WTs are excluded during the calculation of NPV. Altogether, the Expected NPV (ENPV) of the project can be calculated using Equation (12) for the whole study horizon.

$$ENPV_{hybrid} = \frac{1}{n_s} \times \sum_s \sum_i \frac{1}{(1+IR)^i} \times YCF^{(s,i)} \quad (12)$$

where $YCF^{(s,i)}$ is the cash flow of the project in year i of scenario s calculated using Equation (13).

$$YCF^{(s,i)} = YCIF^{(s,i)} - YCOF^{(i)} \quad (13)$$

where $YCIF^{(s,i)}$ is the cash inflow of the project in year i of scenario s and $YCOF^{(i)}$ represents the cash outflow in year i that is independent of the scenarios of the market energy price and the meteorological data.

Considering the incentives that are common in supporting the RES-based projects, especially in the offshore sector (Golroodbari et al., 2021), the cash inflow in this paper is calculated regarding Equation (14).

$$YCIF^{(s,i)} = \begin{cases} 0 & i = 0 \\ 8760 \times (P_f^s - P_e^s) \times (WEP^{(s)} + EPI) & i = 1, 2, \dots, i_p - 1 \\ 8760 \times (P_f^s - P_e^s) \times (WEP^{(s)} + EPI) + R_{salv} & i = i_p \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where $WEP^{(s)}$ is the price of energy in the wholesale market in scenario s , EPI is the incentive of purchasing renewable energy from the offshore renewable farm, P_f^s is the output power of the farm in scenario s calculated using Equation (15), and R_{salv} is the salvage cost of the units calculated by Equation (16).

$$P_f^s = P_e^s + P_{WT}^s + P_{WEC}^s + P_{FPV}^s \quad (15)$$

$$R_{salv} = R_{salv,WT} + R_{salv,WEC} + R_{salv,FPV} \quad (16)$$

where $[R_{salv,WT}; R_{salv,WEC}; R_{salv,FPV}]$ represent the salvage cost of the added WTs, WECs, and FPVs, respectively. However, regardless of the type of the component, the salvage cost of the unit x is calculated using Equation (17) (HOMER Energy)

$$R_{salv,x} = C_{rep,x} \times \frac{LT_x - \left(i_p - LT_x \times INT \left(\frac{i_p}{LT_x} \right) \right)}{LT_x} \quad (17)$$

where $C_{rep,x}$ is the replacement cost of the unit x (i.e. WT, WEC, or FPV), LT_x is the component lifetime, i_p is the project horizon, and $INT(x)$ is the function returning the integer part of x . It should be noted that due to neglecting of the salvage at the end of the lifetime of the units in Equation (17) for the sake of simplicity, the decommissioning costs are neglected as well.

On the other hand, the overall cash outflow of the project can be represented by (18).

$$YCOF^{(i)} = \begin{cases} C_{inv} & i = 0 \\ C_{op}^{(i)} + C_{rep}^{(i)} & i = 1, 2, \dots, i_p \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where C_{inv} is the investment costs while $C_{op}^{(i)}$ and $C_{rep}^{(i)}$ represent the operational, and replacement costs of the project in year i . Supplementary descriptions are provided on some of the cost terms in the following subsections.

2.1.1.1. Investment costs. There are many details that can affect the investment costs of the project in a multi-source offshore power plant especially when the hybridization study is going to be implemented in an existing wind power plant. However, there are assumptions and simplifications applied in this study to provide the possibility of combinational use of the models existing in the literature.

Regarding the combinational implementation of wind-wave sources, there are models in the literature representing the investment costs of these hybrid parks; accordingly, in this study, a model similar to the one given in (Clark et al., 2019) is implemented while some modifications are applied to reflect the effect of the existing wind farm. Furthermore, for the investment costs related to FPV units inside the existing wind farm, the model applied in (Golroodbari et al., 2021) is implemented in this study including a range of values that are considered to cover the different scenarios that may happen in the future.

Altogether, for the multi-source offshore power plant of this work, investment costs of the hybridization project can be calculated using Equation (19).

$$C_{inv} = C_{inv,WT} + C_{inv,WEC} + C_{inv,FPV} \quad (19)$$

where $C_{inv,WT}$, $C_{inv,WEC}$ and $C_{inv,FPV}$ are the investment cost of WT, WEC, and the FPV units that are added to the farm calculated using Equation (20)–(22).

$$C_{inv,WT} = C_{pre,WT} + C_{imp,WT} \quad (20)$$

$$C_{inv,WEC} = C_{pre,WEC} + C_{imp,WEC} \quad (21)$$

$$C_{inv,FPV} = C_{pre,FPV} + C_{imp,FPV} \quad (22)$$

where $[C_{pre,WT}; C_{pre,WEC}; C_{pre,FPV}]$ are the pre-installation costs while $[C_{imp,WT}; C_{imp,WEC}; C_{imp,FPV}]$ represent the implementation costs for the WT, WEC, and FPV. Considering a linear model for the given pre-installation costs regarding the installed capacity that is presented in (Ramos et al., 2022), the cash outflow of the project in $i = 0$ given in Equation (18) can be re-written as Equation (23).

$$YCOF^{(0)} = UC_{pre} \times TIC + C_{imp,WT} + C_{imp,WEC} + C_{imp,FPV} \quad (23)$$

where UC_{pre} is the unit cost of pre-installation, TIC is the total installed capacity calculated by Equation (24), and $[C_{imp,WT}; C_{imp,WEC}; C_{imp,FPV}]$ represent the implementation costs.

$$TIC = n_{WT} \times P_{WT,r} + n_{WEC} \times P_{WEC,r} + n_{FPV} \times P_{FPV,r} \quad (24)$$

where $[P_{WT,r}; P_{WEC,r}; P_{FPV,r}]$ represent the rated power of each WT, WEC, and FPV unit. Furthermore, in Equation (23), the implementation costs of WT and WEC units are calculated using Equation (25) and Equation (26).

$$C_{imp,WT} = C_{design,WT} + C_{const,WT} + C_{inst,WT} \quad (25)$$

$$C_{imp,WEC} = C_{design,WEC} + C_{const,WEC} + C_{inst,WEC} \quad (26)$$

where $[C_{design,WT}; C_{const,WT}; C_{inst,WT}]$ represent the design, construction, and installation costs of the WT while $[C_{design,WEC}; C_{const,WEC}; C_{inst,WEC}]$ represent the same terms for WEC units. However, regarding the model given in (Ramos et al., 2022), it is clear that the cost of the substation is excluded in this paper since the study is done on an existing farm with no expansion on the substation. Moreover, the cost model of the cable connecting the farm to the onshore grid while the cost of the array cables is still included. However, the other details on the calculation of the design, construction, and installation costs of the WT and WEC units are the same as the ones presented in (Clark et al., 2019). Furthermore, as stated, a linear formulation is applied for the calculation of the cost of the offshore FPV units in this paper based on the model given in (Golroodbari et al., 2021). Accordingly, the formulation for the calculation of the cost of FPV in this study can be represented by Equation (27).

$$C_{imp,FPV} = UC_{imp,FPV} \times n_{FPV} \times P_{FPV,r} \quad (27)$$

where $UC_{imp,FPV}$ is the unit cost of implementation of the FPV units in the offshore sector.

2.1.1.2. Replacement costs. As a common strategy, the replacement costs can be modeled as a percentage of the capital cost of the units. Based on (Jahangir et al., 2020a), in this work, the replacement costs of the units are considered to be 90% of the investment costs; according to the description, the replacement costs in Equation (18) are calculated using Equation (28).

$$C_{rep}^{(i)} = 0.9 \times \left(C_{inv,WT} \times z_{rep,WT}^{(i)} + C_{inv,WEC} \times z_{rep,WEC}^{(i)} + C_{inv,FPV} \times z_{rep,FPV}^{(i)} \right) \quad (28)$$

where $[z_{rep,WT}^{(i)}; z_{rep,WEC}^{(i)}; z_{rep,FPV}^{(i)}]$ are the binary values indicating whether the WT, WEC, and FPV should be replaced in year i ; in other words, z is 1 only if the associated year is the end of the lifetime of the component. It should be noted that these binary parameters are calculated prior to the optimization process based on the data available for the lifetime of the units and the project horizon.

2.1.1.3. Operational costs. For the combination of wind and wave sources, the operational cost model developed in (Clark et al., 2019) is applied in this work with minor modifications while considering the insurance cost to be 2% of the O&M costs. Furthermore, based on the description provided in (Golroodbari et al., 2021), the yearly operational cost of the offshore FPV farm is applied as 2% of the investment costs. Accordingly, the overall operation cost related to the hybridization project is modeled as Equation (29).

$$C_{op}^{(i)} = C_{op,WT} + C_{op,WEC} + C_{op,FPV} = 1.02 \times 0.82 \times (133000 \times n_{WT} \times P_{WT,r} + 228536 \times n_{WEC} \times P_{WEC,r}) + 0.02 \times C_{inv,FPV} + C_{adm} \quad (29)$$

where C_{adm} represents the yearly administration costs of the farm and $[C_{op,WT}; C_{op,WEC}; C_{op,FPV}]$ are the operational costs of WT, WEC, and FPV units, respectively.

Table 2

Power output table for the Vestas V164-8 MW wind turbine.

Wind speed (m/s)	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Power (MW)	0.10	0.65	1.15	1.85	2.9	4.15	5.60	7.10	7.80	8.00

2.1.2. Power calculation for the different energy sources based on the meteorological data

2.1.2.1. Wind turbine. In this paper, the power generation model for WTs is implemented based on the data available for Vestas V164-8 MW turbines (Ramos et al., 2022). The data for output power calculation model based on the wind speed for this turbine is given in Table 2 (Vestas V164-8.0 MW Technical Specifications) while the cut-in, rated, and cut-off speeds are 4 m/s, 13 m/s, and 25 m/s, respectively. It should be noted that the power curve is considered acceptably valid for the units with other nominal powers close to 8 MW installed in the offshore sector according to (Ramos et al., 2022). Hence, a conformation factor is applied in the current study to scale up/down the curve for the other nominal power levels studied in the different farms; this way, a better comparison of the hybridization study can be provided in the different studied locations. Furthermore, it should be noted that in this study, instead of fitting a curve like (Ramos et al., 2022), the combinational use of the values given in Table 2 and linear interpolation is applied to determine the output power based on the wind speed.

2.1.2.2. Wave energy converters. In order to calculate the output power of the wave energy converter, the power matrix of the 400 kW CorPower unit is applied in this work (CorPower Ocean - Wave Power, 2021). Accordingly, the power matrix is directly applied to calculate the capability of power generation by a WEC unit in each scenario of the study that is represented by $P_{WEC}^{s,max}$ in this work.

2.1.2.3. PV units. In this paper, the temperature-dependent model represented in (Jamroon, 2022) is applied to calculate the output power of FPV units. Accordingly, the power generation capability of each FPV module is calculated using Equation (30).

$$P_{FPV}^{s,max} = P_{FPV,r} \times \frac{G^s}{G_{STC}} \times [1 + \alpha_p (T_c^s - T_{ref})] \quad (30)$$

where $P_{FPV}^{s,max}$ is the maximum power that can be generated by each FPV panel (W) in scenario s , $P_{FPV,r}$ is the rated capacity of the panel (W), G^s is the solar irradiance in scenario s (W/m^2), G_{STC} is the solar irradiance in standard test condition (W/m^2), α_p is the temperature coefficient ($1/^\circ C$), T_c^s is the cell temperature in scenario s ($^\circ C$) calculated by Equation (31), and T_{ref} is the cell temperature in standard test condition ($^\circ C$).

$$T_c^s = T_a^s + \left[G^s \times \left(\frac{NOCT - 20}{800} \right) \times \left(1 - \frac{\eta_{FPV}}{\tau \alpha} \right) \right] \quad (31)$$

where T_a^s is the ambient temperature in scenario s ($^\circ C$), NOCT is the nominal operating cell temperature ($^\circ C$), η_{FPV} is the reference PV efficiency, τ is transmittance of the PV module surface, and α is the absorbance of the module surface (Zhang et al., 2020).

2.1.3. Technical assessments on the power plant

Regardless of the economics of the project, there are technical assessments that are applied to the power plant before and after optimization. These assessments focus on the variation of the power and energy output of the farm, the utilization of the export cable capacity, the probability of guaranteeing a minimum level of power, and the renewable energy curtailment due to the export system limitation. It should be noted that the technical assessments are implemented on the whole power plant considering the effect of both the existing units and the ones added during the hybridization study. Such assessments can be

important not only for the investor but also for the policymaker since the latter, this way, can assess the benefits provided for the electrical energy system through the incentivization of the hybridization project.

2.1.3.1. Expected curtailed power ratio (ECPR). The Expected Curtailed Power Ratio (ECPR) index, defined by Equation (32), is expressed as percentage in this work while being evaluated for the farm before and after adding the new units regarding the generated scenarios.

$$ECPR = \frac{1}{n_s} \sum_s \left(\frac{P_e^s + n_{WT} \times P_{WT}^{s,max} + n_{WEC} \times P_{WEC}^{s,max} + n_{FPV} \times P_{FPV}^{s,max} - P_f^s}{(P_e^s + n_{WT} \times P_{WT}^{s,max} + n_{WEC} \times P_{WEC}^{s,max} + n_{FPV} \times P_{FPV}^{s,max})} \right) \times 100 \quad (32)$$

2.1.3.2. Expected Capacity Factor of the cable (ECFC). Focusing on the utilization of the capacity of the export cable of the farm as one of the important motivations of the study, in this work, the Expected Capacity Factor of the Cable (ECFC) is calculated and assessed for the existing and hybridized farms regarding the generated scenarios. It should be noted a comprehensive study on cable pooling for an offshore wind power plant in the presence of FPV is given in (Golroodbari et al., 2021). However, expanding such an assessment to the stochastic study of a multi-source farm, the ECFC index expressed in percentage, is formulated as Equation (33) based on the scenarios generated for the hybridization study.

$$ECFC = \frac{1}{n_s} \times \sum_s \frac{P_f^s}{C_{EC}} \times 100 \quad (33)$$

2.1.3.3. Expected low power probability (ELPP). The low power level output of the power plant can happen during many hours of the year for the single-source wind parks; this is one of the unacceptable characteristics of these power plants that is expected to be resolved through hybridization. Accordingly, as another technical assessment on the farm in this work, the low-power probability is assessed before and after hybridization. A previous model for a similar study is provided in (Fusco et al., 2010) through the identification of the number of hours with a specified minimum level of power for the farm. Such an assessment is also implemented in this work regarding the generated scenarios and the index defined as Expected Low Power Probability (ELPP) that is given in Equation (34).

$$ELPP = \frac{1}{n_s} \times \sum_s z_{LP}^s \times 100 \quad (34)$$

in which z_{LP}^s is a binary variable that is calculated using Equation (35).

$$z_{LP}^s = \begin{cases} 1 & P_f^s < P_{LPT} \\ 0 & P_f^s \geq P_{LPT} \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

in which P_{LPT} is the level of power identified as the threshold of the assessment.

2.1.3.4. Variation of the hourly power and monthly energy output of the farm. In this paper Coefficient of Variation (CV) (Kealy, 2023) is applied to assess the potential capability of the new sources of energy in decreasing the power and energy output variations of the farm. Since the variations are calculated based on the time-series of power and energy generation, the historical whole-year data is applied for the evaluation of the CV index in the presence of the stochastically optimized RESs in this section; in other words, the calculation of the index is implemented

Fig. 1. Scenario generation process (WS: wind speed, H: wave height, T: wave period, WEP: wholesale market energy price, G: solar irradiance, and Ta: ambient temperature).

regardless of the generated scenarios. Altogether, the mathematical representation of the CV index for the power output of the farm is given in Equation (36).

$$CV_{P,f} = \frac{\sigma_{P,f}}{M_{P,f}} \quad (36)$$

in which $\sigma_{P,f}$ and $M_{P,f}$ are the standard deviation and mean of the output power of the farm. It should be noted that the assessment of the power output fluctuations only in the hourly time-frame may not successfully reflect the variability of the energy of the farm in longer time scales. Accordingly, as a supplementary assessment in this work, the CV index is also calculated in the monthly time-frame to determine whether a hybrid farm can provide stable energy in all the months and seasons of the year or not (Gideon and Bou-Zeid, 2021); the mathematical formulation of this index is also given in Equation (37).

$$CV_{E,f} = \frac{\sigma_{E,f}}{M_{E,f}} \quad (37)$$

where $\sigma_{E,f}$ and $M_{E,f}$ represent the standard deviation and mean of the energy in the monthly time-frame. Similar to the description given for the CV of the power output of the power plant, the calculation of this index for the energy of the plant is also implemented based on the historical data regardless of the generated scenarios.

2.2. Scenario generation and solution strategy

For implementing the hybridization study in a stochastic framework, different random variables are involved in the mathematical model of the proposed optimization problem. In this work, wind speed, wave height, wave period, solar irradiance, temperature, and wholesale energy market price are the random variables involved in the optimization model. Hence, due to the overall potential dependency of these random variables, the copula theory is used to generate scenarios (i.e., random variables from the joint probability distribution) (Nelsen, 2006).

Furthermore, it should be noted that in this work, the scenario generation process is implemented for the day and night hours independently. Accordingly, the whole yearly data available is firstly divided into day and night hours based on a threshold on solar irradiance value. It should be noted that in this way, the hours with very low irradiance during the days are also categorized as the night hours.

In the next step, among a set of candidate marginal distribution curves including fitted parametric ones and the estimated Gaussian KDE, the one better describing the random variable is selected while the empirical CDF is considered as the reference of comparison. Similar to the solar irradiance, since the temperature is only applied in the solar PV generation model, it is not considered in the scenario generation of night hours. Fitting Gaussian copula is then implemented based on the available data and the developed marginal distributions. In the next step, the scenarios are generated for the day and night hours independently based on the fitted copula; limiting the range of the variables to the ones observed in the historical data, any generated scenario with a variable out of the boundary is excluded from the sets at this step. Finally, the sets of scenarios for day and night hours are combined and fed into the optimization core of the simulation. The overall scenario generation process is demonstrated in Fig. 1 while supplementary information is also provided Section 4.

Focusing on the strategy that is applied to solve the problem based on the implementation of the generated scenarios, it should be emphasized that the characterized hybridization study is linear optimization model with integer variables. In other words, by finding the optimal number and the output power of each of the energy sources for the studied scenarios considering the available capacity of the cable, the optimization problem can be solved using conventional methods available for MILP studies. It should be emphasized that the power generation capability of each single unit regardless of the cable capacity limitation whether for the existing or the new units is determined prior to the optimization based on the generated scenarios. Furthermore, as clarified in Section 2.1.3, the other supplementary assessments that are not involved in the optimization process are applied to the farm before and after hybridization while not affecting the MILP problem solution strategy. The rest of the descriptions regarding the implementation of the MILP optimization to solve the defined hybridization problem are presented in Section 4.

3. Characterization of the implemented studies

The studies implemented in this paper are introduced in this section. Accordingly, the different locations applied for the evaluation of the potential hybridization of the parks are introduced in Section 3.1; then, the sensitivity analyses implemented on the wholesale market price of the energy as well as the implementation cost of the WECs and FPVs are characterized.

3.1. Studied locations and offshore wind power plants

In this paper, three locations have been studied to examine the hybridization framework in different cases. As the first one, WindFloat Atlantic in Portugal is studied as a case of the hybridization using WECs due to the potential of wave energy in this location; however, the solar energy generation is also studied as a supplementary case besides WTs and WECs to further investigate the complementarity of the RES sources in this park. For the second location, Alpha Ventus Park is studied as a hybridization case with the potential of solar energy generation besides WTs due to the ongoing offshore FPV projects in the North Sea; however, WECs are also considered as the other alternative besides the FPVs in this location in the optimization process due to the studies on wave energy in the North Sea in the literature. Finally, due to the potential of wave and solar power generation near Fuerteventura Island, it has also been studied as a case with the possibility of the integration of WECs and FPVs to hybridize the park.

3.1.1. WindFloat Atlantic in Portugal

Windfloat Atlantic is an offshore energy farm near Viana do Castelo in northwest Portugal comprising three semi-submersible WTs each with a nominal capacity of 8.4 MW, and an overall installed capacity of 25.2 MW. Regarding the capacity of the export cable as one of the major focuses of this study, it should be noted that the farm is connected to the onshore grid through an electrical line that is currently operating at 80 MW capacity. Furthermore, it should be emphasized that as the main energy source to hybridize the farm besides the WTs, WECs have been considered in this study for the WindFloat Atlantic case; it is also worth mentioning that there is an assessment for this farm provided in (Ramos

Table 3
Set of the cases applied for the implementation cost of FPV units.

	Low	Medium	High
Code	CFPV-L	CFPV-M	CFPV-H
Ratio of the cost of FPV to the reference value	50%	100%	150%

Table 4
Set of the cases applied for the implementation cost of WEC units.

	Low	Medium	High
Code	CWEC-L	CWEC-M	CWEC-H
Ratio of the cost of WEC to the reference value	75%	100%	125%

Table 5
The cases applied for incentives regarding the wholesale market price.

	Low	Medium	High
Code	EPI-L	EPI-M	EPI-H
Extra payment (%)	25%	50%	75%

Table 6
Other parameters applied in the simulation study.

Parameter	Value
WEC nominal capacity	0.4 MW
Max new WT no.	20
Max WEC no.	400
Max FPV panel no.	800 000
Discount rate	5%
Study horizon (Lifetime of FPV, WT, and WEC)	25 years
WT height	105 m
η_{FPV}	15.67 %
$P_{FPV,r}$	255 W
NOCT	44 °C
G_{STC}	1000 W/m ²
$\tau\alpha$	0.9

et al., 2022) confirming the potential of the site for wave energy generation. However, just as a supplementary study on the complementarity of the different energy sources, the potential of solar energy production in the farm is also investigated in the current work.

3.1.2. AlphaVentus in Germany

AlphaVentus is an existing wind farm in Germany that is located in the North Sea with an overall installed capacity of 60 MW including 12 units of 5 MW turbines with an export cable capacity of 62 MW (Astariz

and Iglesias, 2016). Regardless of the effectiveness of the implementation of solar and wave energy sources in this farm, they are both considered as candidate sources of hybridization besides the wind energy in the studies of this farm due to the possibility of implementation of them in the North Sea in the literature (Golroodbari et al., 2021).

3.1.3. Fuerteventura Island in Spain

This location is selected as the third case of this paper since the potential for hybrid electrical energy generation around this island is already studied in the literature (Veigas and Iglesias, 2014); furthermore, due to the potential for solar FPV implementation around other islands of the area, it has been considered as one of the default options for hybridization study of this case (Ocean Sun and Fred Olsen Renewables). Altogether, in order to examine the developed hybridization model in this case, a farm including 10 WTs with 5 MW nominal power of each unit and a cable capacity of 50 MW is considered at the location proposed in (Veigas and Iglesias, 2014) near the Fuerteventura island.

3.2. Sensitivity analysis regarding the different parameters

3.2.1. Implementation cost of FPV and WEC

As described in Section 2.1.1.1, the implementation cost of FPV units in this paper is modeled based on (Golroodbari et al., 2021) in which a specified range of values for unit cost of FPV is covered and examined. Accordingly, in this work, three main scenarios for low, medium, and high unit costs for FPV are applied based on Table 3. Hence, considering $UC_{imp,FPV} = 1.2$ (€/Watt) for CFPV-M, the other two scenarios named as CFPV-L and CFPV-H are formed applying 50% and 150% of CFPV-M,

Fig. 3. Wind and wave energy generation correlation assessment regarding the different time shift values in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm.

Table 7
Supplementary assessments on the energy generation by each of the studied sources in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm.

	Wind power	Wave power	Solar PV power
CF (%)	37.21	61.15	19.66
CV _P	1.00	0.54	1.41

Fig. 2. Correlation assessment between the energy sources in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm: a) wind and wave b) wind and solar PV c) wave and solar PV.

Fig. 4. Historical data in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm in day hours (WS: wind speed (m/s), H: wave height (m), T: wave duration (s), WEP: wholesale market price of electrical energy (€/MWh), G: solar irradiance (kW/m^2), Ta: ambient temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)).

respectively. Furthermore, in this paper, a similar strategy is applied for the assessment of the effect of the cost of WEC on the results. Accordingly, considering the descriptions given in Section 2.1.1.1 for the calculation of $C_{imp,WEC}$ as the reference case named as CWEC-M, two other cases for the high and low implementation cost scenarios are studied applying 75% and 125% of CWEC-M, independently; these cases for the implementation cost of WEC are given in Table 4.

3.2.2. Incentive of purchasing energy from renewable energy sources

Regarding the descriptions given in Section 2.1.1, in this paper, incentives are applied to the price of energy that is purchased from the farm to model a common strategy for promoting sustainable electricity generation; accordingly, the cases studied for incentivization in this paper are given in Table 5 in which the extra payment values are applied regarding the wholesale energy market price.

4. Simulation results

The simulation results for the hybridization of offshore wind farms concerning the proposed strategy are provided in this section. In order to implement the simulations, the wind speed, wave height/period, temperature, and solar irradiance data are taken from the ERA5 Copernicus dataset (Hersbach et al., 2023). Regarding the wind speed, the 100-m height data is implemented in this study while being transformed to the speed at the height of the turbines of the farm. Furthermore, regarding the wave period, the peak data available in ERA5 is applied in this study; however, it is transformed to the energy period being multiplied by 0.9 (Li et al., 2022).

Due to dramatic changes in energy prices during recent years, reasonable datasets should have been selected to generate the scenarios and implement the planning studies. This is important since the dependency of random variables can strongly affect the solutions of the

optimization while it is reflected in both the historical data of energy price in the wholesale market and the parameters related to energy generation by the wind, wave, and solar sources. In this paper, among the most recent years, the data of 2021 is assumed as one of the most probable scenarios for the future energy cost and is applied as the baseline data for the studies.

The list of values for the other parameters involved in the study is given in Table 6. It should be noted that the discount rate given in the table is considered to be the real value that includes the effect of the nominal one and the inflation rate (Harou, 1983). Moreover, the WT characteristics like the hub height and power curve in all farms are considered the same as the ones existing in WindFloat farm for the sake of simplification while, however, the nominal capacity is selected based on each defined case.

In this study, the Gaussian copula is applied using “Copulas” package in Python (Copulas documentation) to generate the scenarios while being fed automatically to the rest of the developed optimization tool. Finally, it should be noted that the PuLP package (Mitchell et al., 2011) and CBC solver (Coin-or/Cbc) are implemented to solve the defined MILP problem. The simulation results for the different study cases are given and discussed in the following subsections.

4.1. WindFloat Atlantic offshore wind farm

The simulation results for the location of the WindFloat Atlantic park are given in this subsection; this is started with the energy generation potential evaluation that is then followed by the scenario generation results. In the next part, the base case simulation of the sizing study is implemented, and the results of the sensitivity analysis are also given and discussed.

Fig. 5. Generated scenarios for WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm in day hours.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the marginal empirical CDF of historical data and the generated scenarios in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm in day hours.

Table 8

Hybridization study results in the base case of WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm.

	WEC		WT	
	Number	Capacity	No. (total ^a)	Cap. (total ^a)
Optimization result	185	74.0 MW	1 (4)	8.4 (33.6) MW

^a Including existing wind turbines.

4.1.1. Energy generation potential and complementarity of the different sources

In order to simply demonstrate the correlation of each two sources of energy, a strategy similar to the one given for wind-PV in (Golroodbari

et al., 2021) is applied for all three sources of this work and the results are given in Fig. 2 for the real time-series of yearly data; however, it should be emphasized that the demonstration of the correlation is implemented regarding the normalized power generation of each source over the studied time period applying the specifications of the energy conversion systems for each of sources. Accordingly, following the power generation matrix of WEC, discrete values are observed in the plots regarding wave energy in Fig. 2.

According to the results, both wind-solar and wave-solar show a negative correlation in WindFloat Atlantic farm which is desired from the complementarity point of view. However, it should be emphasized that the positive correlation between wind and wave energy is normal, and it can be observed in most of the marine areas; accordingly, in terms

Table 9

NPV of the project and the technical assessments in the base case of WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm.

	ENPV (M€)	ECFC (%)	ELPP ^a (%)	ECPR (%)	CV _{Pf}	CV _{Ef}
Existing farm	–	11.87	56.32	0	1.00	0.32
After optimization	318.08	66.97	2.87	8.01	0.47	0.25

^a 10% of cable capacity threshold.

Fig. 7. Hourly power regarding the real historical data in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm: a) WT, b) WEC, c) power delivered by hybrid park, d) curtailed power.

Fig. 8. Monthly energy generation regarding the real historical data in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm.

Table 10

Hybridization results in the base case of WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm considering FPV as an alternative source.

	WEC		FPV		WT	
	Number	Capacity	Number	Capacity	No. (total ^a)	Cap. (total ^a)
Optimization result	169	67.6 MW	266878	68.05 MW	0 (3)	0 (25.2) MW

^a Including existing wind turbines.

Table 11

NPV of the project and the technical assessments on WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm in the presence of FPV.

	ENPV (M€)	ECFC (%)	ELPP (%)	ECPR (%)	CV _{PF}	CV _{Ef}
Existing farm	–	11.87	56.32	0	1.00	0.32
After optimization	362.71	72.93	2.29	8.91	0.40	0.16

of complementarity, when the wind and wave correlation is not very high, the implementation of them in a hybrid source is considered completely reasonable.

For a supplementary assessment of the wind-wave correlation in the WindFloat Atlantic location, the strategy described in (Fusco et al., 2010) is applied and the values regarding the different time shifts are demonstrated in Fig. 3. According to the results, the peak of the correlation between wind and wave energy in this location appears in low time lags, and the value is almost similar to the one calculated for the case with no time lag; however, it should be emphasized that the

correlation in $\tau(0)$ is less than 0.35 that is also close to the range reported for this area in in (Alday Gonzalez et al., 2022) and it is acceptable for combinational wind-wave energy generation.

Furthermore, regardless of the complementarity of the sources, the consistency of power generation by a new source of energy can provide a strong potential for the hybridization of existing wind power plants through the improvement of the capacity factor of the cable and the farm itself. Accordingly, further assessments are applied to each individual source in the WindFloat Atlantic site and the results are summarized in Table 7.

Fig. 9. Hourly power regarding the real historical data in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm in the presence of FPV: a) WTs, b) WECs, c) FPVs, d) power delivered by hybrid park, e) curtailed power.

Fig. 10. Monthly energy generation regarding the real historical data in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm in the presence of FPV.

Table 12

Effect of the implementation cost of FPV on the hybridization study in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm.

	WEC		FPV		WT	
	Number	Capacity	Number	Capacity	No. (total)	Cap. (total)
Optimization result: CFPV-L	159	63.6 MW	396216	101.03 MW	0 (3)	0 (25.2) MW
Optimization result: CFPV-M	169	67.6 MW	266878	68.05 MW	0 (3)	0 (25.2) MW
Optimization result: CFPV-H	175	70.0 MW	110082	28.07 MW	1 (4)	8.4 (33.6) MW

Table 13

NPV of the project and the technical assessments on the farm for different cases of the cost of FPV.

	ENPV (M€)	ECFC (%)	ELPP (%)	ECPR (%)	CV _{Pf}	CV _{Ef}
Existing farm	–	11.87	56.32	0	1.00	0.32
After optimization: CFPV-L	427.11	73.86	2.37	12.92	0.40	0.13
After optimization: CFPV-M	362.71	72.93	2.29	8.91	0.40	0.16
After optimization: CFPV-H	322.96	70.19	2.17	8.11	0.42	0.20

10% of installed capacity threshold.

Table 14
Effect of implementation cost of WEC on the hybridization study in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm.

	WEC		WT	
	Number	Capacity	No. (total)	Cap. (total*)
Optimization result: CWEC-L	200	80.0 MW	0 (3)	0 (25.2) MW
Optimization result: CWEC-M	185	74.0 MW	1 (4)	8.4 (33.6) MW
Optimization result: CWEC-H	125	50.0 MW	4 (7)	33.6 (58.8) MW

4.1.2. Scenario generation

As described in Section 2.2, in this work, distribution/copula fitting and scenario generation are implemented for the day and night hours, independently. Accordingly, the real yearly data and 10000 generated scenarios for wind speed, wave height, wave period, wholesale energy market price, solar irradiance, and temperature in day hours are given as 2D plots in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively; moreover, for each of them, the marginal empirical Cumulative Distribution Curve (CDF) of the real historical data and generated scenarios are compared in Fig. 6.

It should be noted that in this paper, in order to clearly demonstrate the effect of the cable limitation in curtailments and its effect on the results, the negative and zero prices of energy are neglected being replaced by a negligible small positive value. Furthermore, the number of scenarios generated for the day and night is set based on their ratio in the real historical data while a 10% of peak irradiance is selected as the threshold. However, as stated in Section 2.2, the whole scenarios are finally combined and applied in the stochastic optimization study.

4.1.3. Base case simulation

For Windfloat Atlantic farm, the base case is formed regarding the CFPV-M, CWEC-M, and EPI-M values. As stated in Section 3.1.1, the main optimization studies in the WindFloat farm are implemented regarding the possibility of adding WTs and WECs to the existing farm; accordingly, the results for this combination of energy sources are given

Table 15
NPV of the project and technical assessments on the WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm for different cases of the cost of WEC.

	ENPV (M€)	ECFC(%)	ELPP(%)	ECPR (%)	CV _{Pf}	CV _{Ef}
Existing farm	–	11.87	56.32	0	1.00	0.32
After optimization: CWEC-L	404.92	67.64	2.85	7.93	0.47	0.26
After optimization: CWEC-M	318.08	66.97	2.87	8.01	0.47	0.25
After optimization: CWEC-H	244.80	60.80	6.28	8.13	0.53	0.22

Table 16
Effect of implementation cost of WEC on the hybridization study in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm in the presence of FPV.

	WEC		FPV		WT	
	Number	Capacity	Number	Capacity	No. (total)	Cap. (total)
Optimization result: CWEC-L	188	75.2 MW	248168	63.28 MW	0 (3)	0 (25.2) MW
Optimization result: CWEC-M	169	67.6 MW	266878	68.05 MW	0 (3)	0 (25.2) MW
Optimization result: CWEC-H	82	32.8 MW	318463	81.21 MW	4 (7)	33.6 (58.8) MW

Table 17
NPV of the project and technical assessments on the WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm for different cases of the cost of WEC considering the presence of FPV.

	NPV (M€)	ECFC(%)	ELPP(%)	ECPR (%)	CV _{Pf}	CV _{Ef}
Existing farm	–	11.87	56.32	0	1.00	0.32
After optimization: CWEC-L	442.19	75.34	1.70	11.14	0.38	0.16
After optimization: CWEC-M	362.71	72.93	2.29	8.91	0.40	0.16
After optimization: CWEC-H	302.62	61.18	5.13	9.74	0.49	0.13

in Table 8 while the NPV of the project and technical assessment results on the farm are provided in Table 9. Furthermore, in order to visualize the effect of these stochastically-optimized units on the farm, the power generation results calculated for the whole year of 2021 regarding real historical data are also given in hourly and monthly time-frames in Figs. 7 and 8, respectively. It should be noted that the power for each source (i.e., WT or WEC) is given as the capability of generation while the plant power is demonstrated considering the curtailments due to the cable limitation. Moreover, the monthly energy generation of both sources and the farm are normalized using the maximum value of each of them to provide a clear representation of the effect of hybridization.

According to the results, the highest NPV for the project has been provided through adding 185 WEC units and 1 other WT to the existing three ones; this indicates the great potential of wave energy in the location and the importance of having WTs besides them to take profit from a hybrid farm. The implementation costs of the 8.4 MW WT and 74 MW WEC considering the descriptions given in Section 2.1.1.1 regarding the cost of the units and the cables are 15.1 M€ and 328.9 M€, respectively. It should be emphasized that although the overall installed capacity in the farm after hybridization is 34.5% more than the rated power of the cable, the curtailed energy over the year is 8.01% of the generated energy of the farm. Furthermore, in the presence of the added units, regardless of the economics of the project, the overall fluctuation

Table 18
Effect of EPI on the hybridization study in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm.

	WEC		WT	
	Number	Capacity	No. (total)	Cap. (total*)
Optimization result: EPI-L	172	68.8 MW	0 (3)	0 (25.2) MW
Optimization result: EPI-M	185	74.0 MW	1 (4)	8.4 (33.6) MW
Optimization result: EPI-H	195	78.0 MW	1 (4)	8.4 (33.6) MW

Table 19

NPV of the project and technical assessments on the WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm for different EPI cases.

	ENPV (M€)	ECFC (%)	ELPP (%)	ECPR (%)	CV _{Pf}	CV _{Ef}
Existing farm	–	11.87	56.32	0	1.00	0.32
After optimization: EPI-L	174.58	62.48	4.08	3.64	0.50	0.28
After optimization: EPI-M	318.08	66.97	2.87	8.01	0.47	0.25
After optimization: EPI-H	470.16	68.88	2.72	9.95	0.46	0.24

Table 20

Effect of EPI on the hybridization study in WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm in the presence of FPV.

	WEC		FPV		WT	
	Number	Capacity	Number	Capacity	No. (total)	Cap. (total)
Optimization result: EPI-L	130	52.0 MW	257095	65.56	1 (4)	8.4 (33.6)
Optimization result: EPI-M	169	67.6 MW	266878	68.05	0 (3)	0 (25.2)
Optimization result: EPI-H	185	74.0 MW	286593	73.08	0 (3)	0 (25.2)

Table 21

NPV of the project and the technical assessments on WindFloat Atlantic offshore farm for different EPI cases in the presence of FPV.

	NPV (M€)	ECFC (%)	ELPP (%)	ECPR (%)	CV _{Pf}	CV _{Ef}
Existing farm	–	11.87	56.32	0	1.00	0.32
After optimization: EPI -L	205.30	67.26	3.20	5.82	0.43	0.15
After optimization: EPI-M	362.71	72.93	2.29	8.91	0.40	0.16
After optimization: EPI-H	531.29	75.87	1.72	11.98	0.38	0.15

Fig. 11. Correlation assessment between the energy source in Alpha Ventus offshore farm: a) wind and wave b) wind and solar PV c) wave and solar PV.

Fig. 12. Assessment of the correlation of wind and wave energy generation regarding the different time-shift values in Alpha Ventus offshore farm.

of the power of the park has been considerably decreased due to the complementarity of the sources as well as the overall more stable energy generation by WECs comparing WTs both in the hourly and monthly time scales. Regarding ECFC index, it is clear that due to both the high capacity factor of WECs in the location and the high installed capacity of new RES sources while considering the low capacity of existing units, there is a considerable improvement in the utilization of the export cable

Table 22

Supplementary assessments on energy generation by each of the studied sources in Alpha Ventus offshore farm.

	Wind power	Wave power	Solar PV power
CF (%)	51.59	27.33	13.69
CV _p	0.75	1.12	1.54

Table 23

Sizing result in base case simulation of Alpha Ventus offshore farm.

	FPV		WT	
	Number	Capacity	No. (total) ^a	Cap. (total) ^a
Optimization result	322894	82.34 MW	1 (13)	5 (65) MW

^a Including existing wind turbines.

of the farm. Concentrating on guaranteeing a specified share of power, in the hybridized farm, there is only around 2.87% of the time during the whole year in which the power is less than 10% of the cable capacity. However, since the capacity of the existing units in WindFloat Atlantic

Table 24
NPV of the project and the technical assessments on Alpha Ventus offshore farm.

	ENPV (M€)	ECFC (%)	ELPP (%)	ECPR (%)	CV _{P,f}	CV _{E,f}
Existing farm	–	49.32	22.06	0	0.75	0.26
After optimization	40.82	63.72	11.83	8.87	0.56	0.12

Fig. 13. Hourly power regarding the real historical data in Alpha Ventus offshore farm: a) WT, b) FPV, c) power delivered by hybrid park, d) curtailed power.

Fig. 14. Monthly energy generation regarding the real historical data in Alpha Ventus offshore farm.

Fig. 15. Correlation assessment between the energy source in the Fuerteventura Island study case: a) wind and wave b) wind and solar PV c) wave and solar PV.

farm is much less than the cable capacity, there should be a better reference to make a comparison in this park; accordingly, in this case, the simulations are repeated considering the existence of 13 wind turbines (i. e with the overall capacity of 109.2 MW that is more than the

hybridized farm) and no other WEC; according to the simulation results, even in this case, the ELPP is 29.83% that is much higher than the hybrid farm. It should be emphasized that such improvement is both due to the more stable power generation by the WECs and the complementarity of

Fig. 16. Wind and wave generation correlation assessment regarding the different time shift values in the Fuerteventura Island study case.

Table 25

Supplementary assessment on the energy generation by each of the studied sources in the Fuerteventura island study case.

	Wind power	Wave power	Solar PV power
CF (%)	39.71	57.46	23.03
CV _P	0.78	0.48	1.30

wind and wave energy sources.

In the next step, as stated in Section 3.1.1, the studies in WindFloat are repeated in case of considering FPV as an alternative for hybridization; however, as described, this is a supplementary assessment just for the evaluation of the benefits that can be provided by multi-source farms; in other words, the implementation of WEC is considered the only option besides the WTs for hybridization of WindFloat farm in this paper. Altogether, the results of the hybridization study in this case considering the possibility of solar energy generation are given in Table 10 and Table 11; the implementation costs of the 67.6 MW of WEC and 68.05 MW of FPV in this case are 300.4 M€ and 81.7 M€, respectively. The power generation capability of each source of energy in the farm and the total delivered power through the cable as well as the curtailments are also demonstrated in Fig. 9; finally, the monthly energy generation of the farm is also demonstrated in Fig. 10.

4.1.4. Effect of the implementation cost of FPV

In this section, regarding the descriptions given in Section 3.2.1, the effect of the implementation cost of FPV on the optimization results is investigated. It should be noted that in these studies, CWEC and EPI are maintained the same as the base case. Accordingly, the different cases are examined with respect to Table 3 and the results are given in Table 12 and Table 13.

Table 26

Hybridization results in base case simulation of Fuerteventura island.

	WEC		FPV		WT	
	Number	Capacity	Number	Capacity	No. (total ^a)	Cap. (total ^a)
Optimization result	52	20.8 MW	169788	43.30 MW	0 (12)	0 (60) MW

^a Including existing wind turbines.

Table 27

NPV of hybridization project and the technical assessments in the base case of Fuerteventura island.

	ENPV (M€)	ECFC (%)	ELPP (%)	ECPR (%)	CV _{hf}	CV _{mf}
Existing farm	–	39.92	19.96	0	0.78	0.39
After optimization	99.59	72.36	1.11	13.16	0.38	0.14

4.1.5. Effect of the implementation cost of WEC

The results regarding the different cases of the implementation cost of WEC are given in this section; similar to the previous case, as the default consideration for WindFloat Atlantic farm in this paper, the PVs are excluded from the base study of this section. For the case of EPI-M, the implementation cost of WEC is changed regarding the values given in Table 4 and the results are given in Table 14 and Table 15. Furthermore, the same studies are repeated in the case of the presence of the FPVs considering EPI-M and CFPV-M and the results are given Table 16 and Table 17.

4.1.6. Effect of the incentive of purchasing energy from offshore power plant

Keeping the other parameters the same as the base case, the effect of the different scenarios defined for EPI on the optimization results is provided in this section. Accordingly, the hybridization studies are implemented for each of the cases named EPI-L, EPI-M, and EPI-H and the results are given in Table 18 and Table 19. In the next step, the simulations are repeated for the case in which FPV is also an alternative while CFPV-M is applied as the default unit cost of FPV. The results for this case are given in Table 20 and Table 21.

4.2. Alpha Ventus offshore wind farm

The correlation of each pair of energy sources, the wind-wave correlation assessment regarding the different time-shifts, and the overall energy generation capability assessment results for Alpha Ventus farm are given in Fig. 11, Fig. 12, and Table 22.

Due to the lower wave and solar energy generation capability, there is less strong potential for hybridization in the location of this farm; however, on the other hand, taking the sea condition into account, lower implementation costs can also be expected for FPV in this location. Altogether, for the study of the Alpha Ventus farm, the base case is formed regarding CFPV-L while the incentive and the cost of WECs are

Fig. 17. Hourly power regarding the real historical data in Fuerteventura island: a) WTs, b) WECs, c) FPVs, d) delivered by hybrid park, e) curtailed power.

Fig. 18. Monthly energy generation regarding the real historical data in Fuerteventura island.

maintained as EPI-M and CWEC-M.

According to the description, the base case simulation results for the sizing of energy sources in Alpha Ventus farm are given in Table 23 emphasizing that no WEC is finally selected by the optimization to be added to the farm. On the other hand, although the capacity of the existing units is close to the export cable capacity, one extra WT and a considerable FPV capacity are selected to be added to the farm. The NPV of the project and technical assessment results on the farm in this case are also given in Table 24 while the power/energy generation by the different sources regarding the real historical data are demonstrated in Figs. 13 and 14. According to the results, although there is a considerable capacity of added units, the share of the curtailed energy is still very low; however, the ELPP is still high due to high FPV capacity and the inexistence of WECs in the results. The main effect of hybridization in this case can be observed in the variation of power and energy that are both due to the complementarity of sources and the cable limitation leading to power curtailments; it should be emphasized that the constructive effect of FPV on decreasing the long-term variation of energy generation of the farm can be clearly observed in Fig. 14.

4.3. Fuerteventura island

The correlation of each pair of energy sources, the wind-wave correlation assessment regarding the different time-shifts, and the overall energy generation capability assessment results for the case of Fuerteventura island are given in Fig. 15, Fig. 16, and Table 25.

For Fuerteventura island, similar to the study in WindFloat Atlantic farm, the base case is formed regarding the CFPV-M, CWEC-M, and EPI-M values where, however, all WT, WEC, and FPV are considered as the default candidates in the optimization study. For this case, the hybridization results are given in Table 26 and Table 27; according to the results, a considerable capacity of WECs and FPVs are added to the existing WTs although the cable capacity was considered the same as the rated power of the existing units. By adding the units to the park, a curtailment of 13.16% of the generated energy is observed; however, the capacity factor of the export cable increases from less than 40% to more than 70% which is a considerable improvement. Furthermore, due to the complementarity of the sources, the power and energy variability indexes have also been considerably decreased. Moreover, as given in Table 27, the low-power happens only with 1.11% probability in the

hybrid farm which means guaranteeing the minimum level of power almost all the time; the power/energy output of the park are also shown in Fig. 17 and 18 while the latter clearly demonstrates the stable energy generation capability of the hybrid park although the WT-based one shows a higher variability in energy generation in the different months of the year.

5. Conclusion

In this work, a novel stochastic optimization strategy has been developed for hybridization of existing offshore wind power plants considering the capacity limitation of the export cable. Accordingly, the sizing of the wave energy converters and floating solar PV units is implemented to maximize the economic benefits of the hybridization project while the copula theory is applied to model the dependency of random variables involved in the mathematical model of the problem. The problem is modeled in MILP framework and the wind turbines are also considered as an alternative for the expansion besides the other sources applied for hybridization. The study is then implemented in three different locations and the results are discussed. According to the results, considering the capacity limitation of the export cable of the farms, the combination of the different energy sources can effectively bring economic profit through the complementary energy generation while the curtailment level is within a reasonable range that is less than 15% of the total energy in the whole studied cases; it should be noted that the utilization of the cable is improved to more than 60% in all studied cases in the different locations. Furthermore, the results approved that hybridization could bring several technical benefits besides the improvement of the utilization of the cable capacity. Accordingly, due to the complementarity of the renewable energy sources, the index defined for expected low power probability is less than 12% in all cases of the studied hybrid parks. Furthermore, guaranteeing a minimum level of power for a high share of the time besides the lower variation of power and energy, less capacity of both short-term and long-term storage systems will be needed for the desired operation of electrical energy systems. Altogether, the effective utilization of the available wind farm area and the existing facilities including the export electrical system as well as the decrease of the size of the needed storage system can be regarded as main motivations for the implementation of the hybridization projects in existing offshore wind farms. However, further investigations are needed to clarify the sensitivity of the results to the other parameters involved in the mathematical model. The assessment of the effect of other technical limitations due to harmonics, reactive power, etc. on the delivery of RES generation is also necessitated and will be addressed in future studies. Exploring a comparative analysis between the outcomes derived from the proposed approach and those generated by established commercial software platforms such as RETScreen, or open source solutions like TOPFARM, is also a topic for future work; further investigation on the cost model of the multi-source farms in the studied areas and the effect of units on each other as well as the assessment of the effect of the uncertainty of economic parameters (e.g. the interest rate) on the results are the other details that will be addressed in the future studies of the authors.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ehsan Kazemi-Robati: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Bernardo Silva:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Ricardo J. Bessa:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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